

Impact of Celebrity Endorsement Attributes on Consumer Purchase Intention: Evidence from Pakistan

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Abstract

Despite the popularity of celebrity endorsements in Pakistan, many campaigns fail to influence purchase behavior due to lack of understanding of which celebrity attributes drive consumer intention. This study aims to analyze the impact of celebrity endorsement attributes—celebrity familiarity, likeability, and product-fit—on consumer purchase intention in the Pakistani market. A quantitative research design was adopted, and data were collected through a structured questionnaire from a sample of 100 consumers in Pakistan. Data analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics confirmed acceptable reliability, and Multiple Linear Regression was conducted to test the proposed hypotheses. The results indicate that celebrity familiarity, and product-fit significantly influence purchase intention whereas likeability was not statistically significant. The findings indicate that celebrity familiarity and the logical alignment between the celebrity and the product are stronger drivers of purchase intention, while personal popularity alone is insufficient. Practically, marketers in Pakistan should prioritize product-endorser alignment and familiarity over mere fame when designing advertising campaigns.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement, Match-Up Hypothesis, Source Credibility Model, Celebrity Familiarity, Celebrity Likeability.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, firms are facing intense competition because of wide availability of advertisement campaigns on different platforms which gives birth to advertisement cluttering (Zaheer et al., 2026). To adapt to these conditions, celebrity endorsement has emerged as an effective marketing strategy to heighten brand effectiveness and influence consumer behavior (Dey et al., 2021). The emerging marketing perspective postulates that celebrities act as social and cultural icon and their attributes influence consumer when they engage themselves in any buying decision (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019). In consequence, basis of selection of endorser should not be solely on fame they have but on specific attributes they bring to the brand awareness which collectively serve to bridge the gap between brand awareness and the ultimate intention to purchase (Hameed et al., 2023).

Pakistan also follows this global trend. A number of advertisements on mass media as well social media are bombarded at consumers which create advertisement cluttering and it forces the firms to adopt strategies of celebrity endorsement to communicate their offerings effectively to potential consumers. Historically, Pakistan's market is termed as endorsement savvy as public figures play a lot of role in influencing buying decisions (Qaisar et al., 2026). With this objective in mind, research suggests that celebrity attributes such as attractiveness and product match-up likely to increase the intention to purchase in Pakistan (Khan et al., 2019) while, another research indicates that for established products celebrity's attributes can be secondary to brand loyalty and quality (Jamil & Rameez ul Hassan, 2014). This blend of attitudes of consumers toward different brands creates a complex environment for firms and resultantly they are bound to carefully select which attribute will function well in specific cultural and economic framework of Pakistan.

Though the lens of contemporary marketing theory, celebrity is considered as bundle of different attributes that triggers consumer's purchasing intention (Murugan & Kalimuthu, 2025). In the context of markets like Pakistan, knowing celebrity serves as a starting

point for indulging in any purchasing decision as (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019) argues that the more the celebrity is familiar with the audience the more it builds trust with the targeted audience because that familiarity acts as a social cue for the potential buyers. In addition, the attribute of likeability plays a vital role in creating an emotional connection and this is very strong in Pakistan due to deep public affection with celebrities (Khan et al., 2019). And, the product celebrity fit or in other words the logical match between brand and the endorser is very crucial attribute because it ensures that the message that is being delivered is believable and it reduces consumer's skepticism (Gupta et al., 2015). Regardless of this strategies' widespread use in modern advertising campaigns, it carries risk of financial loss by not being successful (Liu et al., 2026). An issue arises when this advertisement strategy fails to link celebrity's attributes and brand's identity for target audience, and it is noted by (Apejoye, 2013) that lead to skepticism and unfavorable consumer response. Other evidences from Pakistan's society provides mixed conclusions, (Khan et al., 2019) postulates that attributes like attractiveness drive purchase intention in Pakistan and on the other hand (Jamil & Rameez ul Hassan, 2014) argues that for the existing products, brand quality and loyalty are more important than celebrity traits. Ultimately, this academic disagreement triggers the need to study which attributes: familiarity, likeability or fit really determines the purchase intention of general consumers.

The results of this research play a very crucial role for both academic and professional circles. In practice, it will provide marketing managers across Pakistan to tailor their advertisement campaigns effectively by selecting which trait of the celebrity yields most successful results and they can also associate the particular trait of celebrity with the brand that is likely to drive the purchase intent and through this companies can optimize their multimillion advertisement budget and avoid the financial risk associated with brand and celebrity miss match (Apejoye, 2013).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This study is intended to investigate how various celebrity characteristics affect the buying intentions of consumers across Pakistan.

1. **To investigate** the effect of **Celebrity Familiarity** on buyer buying intentions in Pakistani market.
2. **To examine** impact of **Celebrity Likeability** on buying intentions of consumers in Pakistani market.
3. **To estimate** the association between **Celebrity Product Fit** and consumer purchase intention in Pakistani market.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What impact does **Celebrity Familiarity** have on consumer purchase intentions in Pakistan?
2. To what magnitude does **Celebrity Likeability** impact the purchase intentions of consumers in Pakistan?
3. How important is the association between **Celebrity Product Fit** and consumer purchase intentions in Pakistan?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H₁: Celebrity Familiarity has a significant positive effect on purchase intentions of consumers in Pakistan.

H₂: Celebrity Likeability has a significant positive effect on purchase intentions of consumers in Pakistan.

H₃: Celebrity Product Fit has a significant positive effect on purchase intentions of consumers in Pakistan.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In Pakistan, marketing campaigns heavily rely on celebrity endorsement, yet many fails to influence consumer purchase behavior effectively. The key issue lies in selecting the appropriate celebrity attributes—familiarity, likeability, or product fit. Without empirical evidence on which trait drives actual purchase intentions, marketers risk misfit endorsements, wasting both time and financial resources. This study examines the relative impact of these three attributes on consumer purchase intention in Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The tactical use of celebrity endorsement is an extensively acknowledged method for improving marketing effectiveness. As stated by (Liu et al., 2026), the success and failure of this strategy depends on how consumers perceive the particular traits of the endorser. This chapter aims at presenting thorough review of literature to investigate the multidimensional nature of celebrity effect, emphasizing on the roles of familiarity, likeability and product fit. By merging findings from (Khan et al., 2019) and (Apejaye, 2013), this unit investigates how these attributes bridge the space between early brand knowledge and the final purchase intention. The review suggests that the fame of celebrity plays an important role but the psychological connection and the match between celebrity and product is paramount driver of consumer buying behavior in markets like that of Pakistan' (Arif et al., 2026).

This research is supported by two basic theories that explain the process of celebrity endorsement: The Source Credibility Model and the Match up Hypothesis.

The Source Credibility Model is the basic frame of reference utilized to investigate how a messenger's characteristics affect the approval of message. Credit of this theory goes to (Hovland, 1953), who proposed that the success of communication is attached to the observed quality of the sender. (Ohanian, 1990) enlarged this concept by identifying three key dimensions: attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise. As proposed by (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019) consumers face information flood from too many advertisements which makes this model relevant. In such an overloaded environment, the trustworthiness of a celebrity acts as a psychological shortcut or a quality signal. Whenever a buyer is familiar with a celebrity and admires them, they involuntarily assign a higher level of confidence to the offering being endorsed. (Rizomyliotis et al., 2026) postulates that this credibility lessens the consumer's realized risk; when a trusted and valued figure endorses a brand, the buyer feels safer and intends to buy it. Consequently, this model clarifies why Familiarity and Likeability are powerful economic drivers that indulge customers in buying from that brand.

The source credibility model focuses on endorser's personal traits, while the **Match up Hypothesis** prioritizes logical fit between the celebrity and the brand (Millán et al., 2026). This theory which is well explained by (Apejoye, 2013) suggests that the effectiveness of an endorsement relies on intensity of harmony between the endorser's image and the product category. Research by (Jamil & Rameez ul Hassan, 2014) and (Khan et al., 2019) suggest a misalignment between endorser's image and brand's identity may in fact damage or harm the brand. For instance, a celebrity who is known for his luxurious lifestyle shows up in an advertisement of low cost or basic necessity products, the consumer may consider that endorsement as insincere or motivated by money only. This inconsistency builds distrust and lowers the consumer's intent to buy.

This portion provides a comprehensive analysis of main variables included in the research model. By investigating the individual component of celebrity endorsement: familiarity, likeability and product-fit, this review examines how these factors collectively affect the psychological state of a consumer. The subsequent discussion consolidates the empirical findings to make the conceptual link between these traits and the final establishment of purchase intention.

Source Credibility Model given by (Hovland, 1953) and (Ohanian, 1990) advocate that for any persuasive message to be validated, the provenance must first hold a recognized status recipient's atmosphere. **Familiarity** functions as the basic mental gateway through which a marketing campaign must pass to be successful; if audience do not recognize the endorser, the successive traits of expertise and trustworthiness could not be processed. In Pakistan, where brands compete fiercely for consumer attention, familiarity serves as a starting point that stands out. (Dey et al., 2021) suggests that the more cognitively accessible a celebrity is to the general public, the more likely the end-user is to pause and engage with advertisement rather than ignoring it.

The mere exposure effect states that the frequent exposure to a cue, in this study's case, celebrity, leads to natural liking and a sense of security. As stated by (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019), familiarity not only aids awareness; it enhanced the perceived trustworthiness of the endorser and make endorser feels more like a familiar entity rather than an strange actor in advertisement. This feeling of familiarity acts as a connection, as argued by (Khan et al., 2019), changing a conceptual brand promise into a relevant and reliable recommendation.

According to (Mtutsa & Mhaka, 2025), advertisement campaigns that feature highly famous celebrities result in considerably higher recall rates among consumers contrasted to those that feature less famous celebrities. Either this familiarity is gained through long term careers in traditional media or social media, this provides endorser with the social network necessary to control general public opinion. Conclusively, as familiarity offers essential visibility for a brand, its main function within this research is to provide the beginning layer of trust required to shift a consumer from mere acknowledgment to an active buying decision.

Celebrity likeability is envisioned as an extent to which a consumer holds positive affection, admiration and emotional regard for a celebrity. This aspect is an important feature of source attractiveness within the Source Credibility Model, which postulates that a celebrity's fascination and recognized personality are as important as their good looks (Hovland, 1953; Ohanian, 1990). Moreover, (Dey et al., 2021) argue that likeability

functions as the emotional engine of an advertisement campaign, when consumer values a celebrity, they are likely to accept the message being delivered, making a more acceptable environment for the brand's promotion claims.

The strategic significance of likeability in marketing falls in its distinct capability to lessen the natural resistance consumers feel toward being sold a product. As stated by (Apejoye, 2013), when consumers like a celebrity the advertisement targeted at them is considered by them as a personal recommendation from a respected role model. (Tarigan et al., 2023) suggests that likeability supports in making a favorable brand image, which performs the act of mediator in the relationship between celebrity and consumer's eventual behavior. This mechanism is often driven by halo effect in which consumer's positive feelings for the celebrity are instantly moved to the endorsed product (Gupta et al., 2015). By taking advantage from this emotional bond, brands can circumvent consumers doubts and ingrain a sense of trust that is essential for driving purchase intention.

As suggested by (Dey et al., 2021) that when a famous celebrity endorses a product it is sure that the advertisement will be noticed, but when a likeable celebrity endorses a product the consumers will choose this over competitive brands. Research by (Gupta et al., 2015) and (Khan et al., 2019) ensures that this psychological connections is an important and direct estimator of if a consumer will change from seeing an advertisement to forming a purchase intention. Finally, likeability changes a well-known celebrity into a persuasive advocate, making it an important variable for any effective endorsement campaign in Pakistan.

Celebrity Product fit, is cited as match up or agreement, is explained as the extent to which consumer perceives the harmony between celebrity's public image and the functional natural of product being endorsed (Khan et al., 2019). This variable is theoretically given by the Match up Hypothesis which postulates that success of an endorsement is not dependent on celebrity's fame but on relevance of celebrity to the brand (Apejoye, 2013). Research of (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019) suggest that when this fit is high in it ensures that the transfer of attributes from endorser to the brand is believable. Contrary, when this fit is missing the endorsement will be perceived as purely commercial transaction and which results in low degree of consumer influence (Tarigan et al., 2023).

The importance of fit lies in its ability to approve of the endorsement in the eyes of doubtful audience. (Tarigan et al., 2023) argues that even the well-known celebrity that is liked by masses can fail to effectively endorse a product if a product's functions do not fit with the personality of that endorser. This is also backed up by the research of (Gupta et al., 2015) which suggests that strong fit between endorser and the brand leads to believability. (Adeoye, 2013) argues that fit acts as an important filter, it guarantees that the celebrity's affection and familiarity are made use of towards a relevant goal, rather than the being wasted on a contradictory product.

Purchase Intention can be defined as the probability that a consumer will buy a product after seeing an advertisement campaign (Khan et al., 2019). In this research, it represents the dependent variable that determines the effectiveness of a celebrity's endorsement campaign. As stated by (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019) intent to buy is not an immediate

action but a thought processing mechanism in which consumers indulge themselves in to check credibility and relevance of the endorser. (Tarigan et al., 2023) argues that intention measures the actual buying behavior of the consumer in the real market scenario. Moreover, (Apejoye, 2013) suggests that for some consumers this intention to buy is negotiation between likeability for an endorser and functional benefits of the product.

The development of purchase intention is not a result of single factor, rather it is an outcome of familiarity, likeability and product fit working altogether. According to (Jamil & Rameez ul Hassan, 2014), in Pakistan the purchase intention is very high when consumer develops trust bond with the endorser. This bond starts with familiarity, maintained by likeability and eventually validated by product fit (Khan et al., 2019). According to (Gupta et al., 2015), if any of these pillars are weak, for instance, if a celebrity does not fit for the product, the consumer's purchase intention will be low due to perceived insincerity. (Tarigan et al., 2023) suggests that the purchase intention of consumers reflect the brand attitude and the celebrity acts as a catalyst that changes neutral attitude into a definitive purchase plan to buy.

Hypothesis Development

Celebrity Familiarity: The connection between celebrity familiarity and purchase intention is grounded in the mental ease of recognition. According to (Osei-Frimpong et al., 2019) and (Apejoye, 2013) familiarity acts as beginning signal that reduces consumer skepticism. When a consumer identifies a celebrity, the cognitive barrier towards the advertisement is lowered, making a path for the brand message to be effective. Based on the thorough review of literature, it is postulated that the greater the familiarity the greater the inclination of consumer towards a brand being endorsed.

H₁: Celebrity Familiarity has a significantly positive impact on consumer purchase intention.

Celebrity Likeability: As stated by (Khan et al., 2019) and (Dey et al., 2021) the optimistic feelings a consumer has for a celebrity are shifted to the brand through halo effect. Moreover, this psychological bond between celebrity and consumer is a powerful motivator where consumers align their purchasing habits with the celebrity they admire (Jamil & Rameez ul Hassan, 2014). Thus, it is proposed that the more the celebrity is liked the stronger the consumer's purchase intent to purchase the product would be.

H₂: Celebrity likeability has a significantly positive impact on consumer purchase intention.

Celebrity-Product Fit: Lastly, the alignment between the celebrity and the product fit functions as the final validator of the endorsement sincerity. (Tarigan et al., 2023) and (Gupta et al., 2015) suggest that in absence of this alignment the most famous celebrity could fail to effectively endorse the product. In markets like Pakistan, functional and figurative alignment is of vital importance for creating a believable message (Khan et al., 2019). Thus, when consumers perceive fit between the product and celebrity, the intention to purchase will be very high.

H₃: Celebrity Product fit has significantly positive impact on consumer purchase intention.

Conceptual Framework

Figure-1 Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative research design is instituted to measure the relationship among independent variables (familiarity, likeability and product fit) and dependent variable (intention to purchase). According to (Selvi & Mahadewi, 2026), a causal design is important when the basic objective is to investigate the degree to which one variable predicts the change in another. By implementing a structured survey method, this study seeks to present empirical proof that can be standardized to a wider population in the context of the emerging markets.

Research philosophy

This study adopts positivism. This philosophy is based on the idea that reality is objective and can be measured through scientific methods and statistical analysis. According to (Dey et al., 2021), this approach is very useful because it allows the researcher to remain objective and in this study this approach ensures that results regarding the celebrity endorsement are based on quantifiable data rather than subjective interpretation. This harmony is important for testing the hypothesis obtained from the Source Credibility Model and the Match up Hypothesis.

Population and Sampling

Target Population: Consumers whose age is not less than 15 years and are exposed to celebrity endorsed advertisements on television and digital media.

Sampling Technique: A non-probability convenience sampling technique is applied. This technique is routinely used in consumer behavior studies as it facilitates data collection from accessible participants who regularly consume media content.

Sample Size: A sample size of 100 respondents was considered adequate for exploratory quantitative analysis in consumer behavior studies.

Data Collection Procedure

Primary Data Collection: Primary data is collected for this study using Google Forms, sent to respondents. As this study focuses on consumers in Pakistan, for this purpose people residing in different cities participate by filling the online form.

Measurement of Variables: 5-point Likert Scale ranging from 1= **Strongly Disagree** to 5= **Strongly Agree**

Results

This chapter is aimed at providing statistical analysis of primary data collected through questionnaires for this study. The objective of this study is to examine the impact of celebrity endorsement and for the this purpose this research considers three independent variables (Celebrity Familiarity, Likeability, and Product-Fit) and one dependent variable (Intention to Purchase) and analyze impact of independent variables on dependent variable. For data analysis IBM SPSS Statistics is utilized.

Table-1 Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Variables	Category	Frequency(n)	Percentage
Gender	Male	67	67.0
	Female	33	33.0
Age Group	15-25	9	9.0
	26-35	60	60.0
	36-40	21	21.0
	46 and above	10	10.0
Education Level	Undergraduate	73	73.0
	Post Graduate	20	20.0
	Professional/Others	07	7.0
Media/TV usage	1-2 Hours	42	42.0
	3-5 Hours	48	48.0
	More than 5 Hours	10	10.0
Total		100	100.0

Reliability Analysis: The reliability test is conducted using Cronbach's Alpha. In academic researches, a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient more than 0.7 or higher is valid and demonstrate reliability. Variables, both independent and dependent, we evaluated. After analysis it is proved that all the constructs exceed the acceptable threshold. The table below shows coefficient value of each variable.

Table-2 Reliability Analysis

Construct	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Familiarity	4	0.726
Likeability	4	0.749
Product Fit	4	0.829
Intention to Purchase	4	0.822

Correlation Analysis: Pearson coefficient is computed to assess the strength and direction of the variables. Moreover, it aims at checking the issue of multicollinearity. Upon the test run, the results indicated positive and statistically significant relationship with $p < 0.001$ across all variables. Regarding variables, independent variable Celebrity Familiarity demonstrates strongest correlation with dependent variable Intention to Purchase ($r=0.595$), while Likeability ($r = 0.572$) and Product-fit ($r = 0.534$).

Moreover, the analyses suggested that independent variables have positive relationship with each other. Celebrity Familiarity and Likeability have ($r = 0.672$). Besides, Familiarity is also positively correlated with Product Fit ($r = 0.539$) and Likeability ($r = 0.591$). Concluding, all correlation coefficients remain well below the 0.8 which suggest that absence of multicollinearity among independent variables. This relation allows the analysis to move further to run Multiple Linear Regression analysis.

Table-3 Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	1	2	3
Familiarity	1		
Product Fit	0.539	1	
Likeability	0.672	0.591	1
Intention to Purchase	0.595	0.534	0.572

Multiple Linear Regression: To analyze the impact of independent variables (Celebrity Familiarity, Likeability, and Product-Fit) on dependent variable (Intention to Purchase) **Multiple Linear Regression** was conducted. This analysis suggest that overall model is significant, F-test (3, 96), $p < 0.001$ indicated that all the independent variables included in this study define the intention to purchase. The $R^2 = 0.441$ suggest that 44 per cent of variance in intention to purchase can be explained by celebrity endorsement variables which additionally suggests that there is highly explanatory effect. Moreover, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of all variables were below the threshold of 5 (Familiarity = 1.931, Likeability = 2.106 and Product Fit = 1.630) which rejects the notion that multicollinearity is not confounding problem in regression model. An evaluation of standardized coefficients (β) suggest different results regarding each variable. Celebrity Familiarity has strongest predictor of Intention to Purchase ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 3.063$, $p = 0.003$). Product Fit is also significant explanatory of Intention to Purchase ($\beta = 0.230$, $t = 2.365$, $p=0.020$). But, the relationship between Likeability and Intention to Purchase marginally missed the threshold for significance ($\beta = 0.218$, $t = 1.968$, $p = 0.052$).

Table-4 Multiple Linear Regression Results

Model	Unstandardized β	Std. Error	Standardized β
Constant	0.779	0.382	
Familiarity	0.334	0.109	0.325
Likeability	0.239	0.122	0.218
Product Fit	0.244	0.103	0.230

Summary of Hypothesis: According to results of Multiple Linear Regression, following determinations have been made regarding the proposed conceptual framework

- **Celebrity Familiarity – Intention to Purchase:** p value is 0.003, therefore this relation is **Supported**.
- **Likeability – Intention to Purchase:** p value is 0.052, therefore this relation is **Not Supported**.
- **Product Fit – Intention to Purchase:** p value is 0.020, there relation is **Supported**.

Discussion

This study aims at empirically investigating the operational effect of multidimensional celebrity endorser attributes – celebrity familiarity, likeability and product fit – on consumer’s intention to purchase in Pakistan.

The statistical results indicate that celebrity familiarity has positive impact on consumer’s intention to purchase, therefore **H₁ is highly supported**. This validates traditional Source Credibility Model, indicating that most noticeable and publicly liked endorsers minimize perceived risk when judged by target audience. This predictive relationship aligns with the findings of (R. Ali et al., 2025) who prove that primary visibility within public discourse dominates choices in Pakistan. Thus, the more celebrity is familiar with public the more it influences target audience which will result in high rate of intention to purchase.

The empirical results also indicate that celebrity product-fit has positive impact on consumer’s intention to purchase, meaning **H₃ is supported**. This supports the foundational Match-Up hypothesis, indicating that the logical alignment between the product and endorser validate a marketing campaign. It suggests that when consumers perceive the celebrity endorsing a product is perfect match, the likelihood of purchasing from that brand will increase because it acts as personal recommendations for that product from a celebrity. This finding is also supported the by the research by (S. M. F. Ali et al., 2024) who prove that consumers often look for credibility of endorser when making any purchase intention. Hence, functional congruence is necessary for any endorsement drive to be successful.

In contrast, celebrity likeability does not have positive impact on consumer’s intention to purchase, therefore H₂ is **not supported**. This discloses that while consumers like public figures for entertainment but that likeability alone does not convert into commercial trust. (Arif et al., 2026) argue that for an endorsement to be successful, the celebrity chosen should be familiar with target audience to lower the intensity of consumer skepticism and the endorser’s lifestyle must align with the product being endorsed.

Theoretical Implications: This research contributes significantly to the field of consumer behavior. First, it adds skepticism to traditional (Ohanian, 1990) model which suggests that all dimensions of credibility are equal important but the findings of this study suggest that Likeability does not yield intention to purchase because consumers include themselves in thought processing mechanism before making any purchase decision. Second, this study emphasizes the Match Up hypothesis, proving that the alignment between celebrity and product is necessary in order to tailor any advertisement campaign.

Managerial implications

- Celebrity Product-fit is more important than affection because as this study suggests mere likeability does not yield intention to purchase rather consumer check the trustworthiness of the endorser by analyzing the Celebrity-Product fit.
- Young population is more influenced by endorsement campaign because they are more active on digital and social media as compared to the older ones as this study suggest people age between 15 and 25 have highest score of endorsement influence.
- Usage of media play a very important role in celebrity endorsement because the more time people spent on media the more they are exposed to endorsement as this study suggests people who spent 3-5 hours daily on media are more likely to get influenced.

Conclusion:

This study highlights the role of celebrity endorsement in today's saturated markets where consumers struggle to differentiate and find credible and convincing information. Given the competitive landscape, there is a greater need for organizations to choose the right endorsement strategy to effectively influence consumer behavior. The results of this study prove that celebrity familiarity and fit of celebrities with the product play important role in consumer purchase intention in Pakistan but celebrity likeability does not play a significant role in a consumer's purchasing decision.

The findings indicate that consumers are not only looking up to or fond of a celebrity; they are also considering other factors when deciding to buy a product. Rather, they check if the star is known, reliable and seems to be a suitable fit for the product being promoted. The result is consistent with the Source Credibility Model and the Match-Up Hypothesis, that is, familiarity and functional congruence between celebrity and product enhances endorsement campaign effectiveness. However, if you simply went with the popularity or likeability, alone, you would not build commercial trust among consumers. From a managerial point of view, the study has revealed that marketers, when choosing celebrities for an endorsement, should consider their public recognition level and/or their relevance to the endorsed product, not just their popularity or attractiveness. This can better align consumers and improve the effectiveness of the ad as well as minimize the chances of endorsement fails. Furthermore, the study says younger consumers are more likely to be swayed by celebrity endorsements, especially in the 15-25 age group who are more exposed to digital and social media.

In conclusion, this research helps in the overall body of knowledge pertaining to celebrity endorsement in emerging markets as it offers empirical evidence from Pakistan. The research provides valuable perspectives for advertising practitioners and agencies looking to maximize their endorsement approach in a more competitive environment.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the sample size was limited to 100 respondents, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to the wider population of Pakistan. Second, the study used a non-probability convenience sampling technique, which may introduce sampling bias. Third, the research focused only on consumers in Pakistan; therefore, the results may differ across cultures, industries, and economic environments. In addition, the study adopted a cross-sectional design, which captures consumer perceptions at a single point in time and may not reflect changing consumer attitudes over

time. Future studies should use larger and more diverse samples, adopt probability sampling techniques, and conduct comparative cross-cultural or industry-specific analyses to provide broader insights into celebrity endorsement effectiveness.

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